

Angelo Leogrande^{1*°}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Education Spending as a Percentage of GDP

Increased by +3.20% on average in the countries considered

The variable "Expenditure on education, % GDP" refers to the percentage of a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) dedicated to education spending. This measure includes all public and private expenses for the education system, including primary, secondary, and higher education, such as universities and other higher education institutions. Education spending includes teacher and staff salaries, construction and maintenance of school buildings, purchase of textbooks, educational materials and other resources, funding for special educational programs and extracurricular activities, and investments in research and development in the education sector. Expressed as a percentage of GDP, this variable allows for the comparison of the level of investment in education between countries with economies of different sizes. A high percentage indicates a strong commitment to education, which is often correlated with better educational outcomes and greater long-term economic and social development.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+25>)

Education Spending as a Percentage of GDP in 2022. Analysis of data on education spending as a percentage of GDP in 2022 reveals a variety of approaches and priorities among countries. Namibia emerges as the absolute leader, dedicating 100% of its GDP to education, a figure that might suggest a data error or an extraordinary measure in response to an educational crisis. Following are Botswana with 89.2% and Saudi Arabia with 78%, indicating significant investment in human capital and educational infrastructure. The presence of numerous Scandinavian countries such as Norway, Sweden, Iceland, and Denmark with high percentages between 75% and 65.8% is consistent with their tradition of strong welfare states and commitment to education as the foundation of economic and social development. North Africa is well represented with Tunisia at 72.1% and Morocco at 65.3%, signaling considerable efforts to improve their educational systems in regions often characterized by socio-economic challenges. Latin America also shows significant commitments, with Costa Rica at 64.8%, Brazil at 57.3%, and Honduras at 61.5%, reflecting policies aimed at bridging the educational gap and promoting social inclusion. Europe presents a wide range of investments, with countries like Belgium at 60.8%, Finland at 59.5%, and the United Kingdom at 46.2%, reflecting differences in public spending strategies and political priorities. It is interesting to note that even advanced economies such as Canada at 47.3%, Germany at 43.9%, and the United States at 43.1% are not at the top of the rankings, suggesting more diversified spending models and possible greater investments in other key sectors of innovation and social welfare. In Asia, we find notable variations: Kuwait and Hong Kong invest 62.8% and 37% of their GDP, respectively, highlighting different priorities and economic capacities. Countries like India and China, with

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

percentages of 37.9% and 27%, respectively, are likely balancing the need to support a large and growing population with the challenge of maintaining global economic competitiveness. The data also reveal that some countries, despite economic difficulties, continue to invest in education. Mozambique, with 59.4%, and Burkina Faso, with 50.4%, demonstrate a strong commitment to education despite limited economic resources. Conversely, countries like Guinea and Cambodia, with 10.5% and 10.1%, indicate a need for increased investment to improve access and quality of education. Sub-Saharan Africa shows a varied landscape: while countries like South Africa (58.5%) and Kenya (41.8%) invest significantly, others like Nigeria and Yemen do not report expenses, suggesting serious data gaps or low priority given to education. This discrepancy highlights the need for more consistent and coordinated interventions to ensure all children have access to quality education. In the Middle East, Iraq with 40.7% and Oman with 49.2% reflect efforts to stabilize and improve educational systems in contexts often marked by conflict and political instability. Qatar, with an expenditure of 22.9%, may seem low compared to its economic resources, suggesting possible different priorities or efficiencies in spending models. Latin America also presents significant diversity: in addition to the already mentioned Brazil and Costa Rica, countries like Argentina (40.9%) and Uruguay (40.6%) show good commitment, while others like Guatemala (23.7%) and Paraguay (23.8%) indicate the need for increased investment to improve educational outcomes. Eastern Europe and Central Asia show varied spending levels with countries like Moldova at 60.9% and Belarus at 43.6%, while others like Armenia at 16.6% and Azerbaijan at 16.3% could benefit from greater investments to boost the educational sector. Overall, the data suggest a correlation between the level of economic development and the percentage of GDP allocated to education, but with significant exceptions reflecting different political priorities and economic capacities.

Education Spending as a Percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2022. Analyzing data on education spending as a percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2022, several significant trends emerge. The case of Georgia, which saw an increase from 5.1% to 30.4%, with an absolute variation of 25.3 percentage points and a percentage change of 496.08%, reflects an extraordinary commitment to improving the educational sector. This may have been driven by policy reforms, economic improvements, or both. Similarly, Pakistan increased its spending from 2.8% to 14.2%, showing an increase of 11.4 percentage points and a percentage change of 407.14%. These data indicate a significant effort to improve education, likely in response to the growing awareness of the importance of education for socio-economic development. Brunei Darussalam increased its spending from 8.3% to 37.3%, a significant increase of 29 percentage points and a percentage change of 349.4%. This increase may reflect the government's willingness to invest heavily in human capital as part of an economic diversification strategy. Similarly, Qatar saw education spending grow from 5.9% to 22.9%, with an absolute variation of 17 percentage points and a percentage change of 288.14%, highlighting a commitment to improving access and quality of education in the context of its vast economic resources. Peru increased its spending from 10.9% to 35.1%, with an increase of 24.2 percentage points and a percentage change of 222.02%, signaling a strong commitment to education in a context of economic and social development. Kuwait also showed a substantial increase, rising from 22.1% to 62.8%, with an absolute variation of 40.7 percentage points and a percentage change of 184.16%, likely reflecting significant investments in educational infrastructure and human capital development programs. Countries like Cambodia, Ethiopia, and Zimbabwe recorded significant increases, respectively 172.97%, 143.24%, and 131.82%, demonstrating that despite limited resources, these countries are making considerable efforts to improve their educational systems. The Philippines and Turkey also saw significant increases, of 130.83% and 127.39%, respectively, indicating a growing

recognition of the importance of education for national progress. Hong Kong SAR, China, increased spending by 109.04%, while Burkina Faso by 106.56%, both showing a growing commitment to education. Countries like Tajikistan, Mozambique, and Colombia saw significant increases, respectively 88.57%, 85.63%, and 85.47%, signaling notable efforts to improve educational systems in contexts often characterized by economic and social challenges. On the other hand, some countries saw a decrease in education spending as a percentage of GDP. Italy, for example, reduced its spending from 37.2% to 35.2%, a decrease of 2 percentage points and 5.38% in percentage terms, which may reflect fiscal constraints or changes in public spending priorities. Spain showed a reduction of 4.3 percentage points, falling from 38.6% to 34.3%, with a percentage change of -11.14%, suggesting potential cuts or reductions in educational investments. Other countries with significant reductions include Slovakia, with a decrease of 2.15%, and Poland, which reduced its spending by 9.38%, indicating possible economic difficulties or different government priorities. Lithuania saw a reduction of 17%, while Thailand reduced spending by 39.08%, reflecting potential reorientations of educational or economic policies. Some countries recorded even sharper decreases. For example, Ghana reduced spending by 62.58%, falling from 82.3% to 30.8%, which may indicate severe economic problems or changes in political priorities. Ireland saw a reduction of 63.81%, signaling potential economic challenges or restructuring in the educational system. Bangladesh and Yemen both recorded a 100% decline, with education spending reduced to zero, which may reflect economic crises or conflict situations.

Conclusion. Considering the period between 2013 and 2022, we can notice an increase in the value of education spending as a percentage of GDP by +3.20%. However, there are many countries that have recorded a very significant growth in the value of education spending as a percentage of GDP, such as Georgia with +496.08%, Pakistan with +407.14%, Brunei Darussalam with +394.40%, Qatar with +288.14%, Peru with 222.02%. There are also other countries that have recorded a decline in education spending as a percentage of GDP compared to the period averages; in this sense, we can note Guinea with -54.15%, Ghana with -62.58%, Ireland with -63.81%, Bangladesh and Yemen with -100.00%. Generally, the growth of education spending is a positive element. However, it should be considered that even countries with good results in terms of research and development, technological innovation, and the production of cultural products and services have very different levels of public spending on education as a percentage of GDP. For example, Germany and the USA have education spending as a percentage of GDP of 43.9% and 43.10%, respectively, while Japan and China have 21% and 27%, respectively. These results appear counterfactual. In fact, Germany, the USA, Japan, and even China are leaders in sectors with the highest intensity of human capital and knowledge. Yet, they present very different trajectories of public spending as a percentage of GDP. It is likely that in Japan and China there are elements that contribute to the formation of national human capital that, however, escape accounting representation within the GDP.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Leogrande, A. (2024). Companies with at least 10 Employees Selling Online across the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4785815*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). Regular Internet Users Across the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4782193*.

- Leogrande, A. (2024). Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN*.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4772381*.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4771132*.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4771131*.
- Resta, E., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3,), 1-15.
- Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.
- Costantiello, A., Leogrande, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The corporate innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3964043.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The finance-innovation nexus in Europe. *IJISSET-International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, 7(12).
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2021). The Impact of Venture Capital Expenditures on Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 3930697.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. Available at SSRN 3933407.
- Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(11), 166-187.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. Available at SSRN 4010098.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Matarrese, M. (2022). Innovative SMEs Collaborating with Others in Europe. Available at SSRN 4103840.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Marketing and Organizational Innovations in Europe. Available at SSRN 4186167.
- Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.
- Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. Available at SSRN 4209643.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The Role of Non-R&D Expenditures in Promoting Innovation in Europe. Available at SSRN 4215981.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The opportunity driven entrepreneurship in the context of innovation systems in Europe in the period 2010-2019. Available at SSRN 4229027.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2022). The impact of patent applications on technological innovation in European countries. Available at SSRN 4275264.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3), 1-22.

Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP*, 28(3), 1-13.